

SEVEN STEPS TO PUBLIC SPEAKING SUCCESS

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Abstract This article covers the means of developing a public oratory culture and is analyzed through seven steps.

Key words: public speaking, Preparation, Tone of Voice, Storytelling, public speakers.

Аннотация В данной статье рассматриваются средства развития культуры публичного ораторского искусства и анализируются в семь этапов.

Ключевые слова: публичное выступление, подготовка, тон голоса, повествование, публичные ораторы.

Public speaking, also called oratory or oration, has traditionally meant speaking in person to a live audience. Today it includes speaking, formally or informally, to an audience through technology — live, pre-recorded, or at a distance.

Confucius, the philosopher and public speaking scholar, thought a good speech should impact individual lives, regardless of whether they were in the audience.[1] He believed that someone of power could influence the world with words and action.[1]

Although evidence of public speaking training exists in ancient Egypt, the first known writing on oratory is 2,000 years old from ancient Greece. This work elaborates on principles drawn from the practices and experiences of ancient Greek orators.

Aristotle was one who first oratory teachers to use definitive rules and models. One of his key insights was that speakers always combine, to varying degrees, three things: reasoning, which he called Logos; credentials, which he called Ethos; and emotion, which he called Pathos. Aristotle's work became an essential part of a liberal arts education during the Middle Ages and the Renaissance. The classical antiquity works by the ancient Greeks capture how they taught and developed the art of public speaking thousands of years ago.

The advantages of public speaking are that you are seen as an expert because why would you be asked to speak if you weren't? What you say and how you convey yourself can be absorbed for a long time after you've spoken, especially with shared online video. If you are memorable then your brand is remembered too. You will be seen as the "go-to" person on the subject at a later time. There are also the networking advantages of being seen and introduced to many people at once.

While some experience a buzz from being in front of a crowd, the rest of us are all prone to experiencing butterflies and lack of sleep the night before. Even the most seemingly confident business people can be reduced to a mess when put in front of an audience. This can be overcome with the right training and preparation.

Here are seven key principles of public speaking we teach when coaching our clients:

1. Preparation

First you need to decide what the purpose of your talk really is. What is the "take-home" message you want to give your audience? Organise your talk accordingly, focusing sharply on your intended message. Keep repeating your key message throughout.

Avoid over-rehearsing. Rather than memorising the entire content of your presentation, understand the concept as this will help you develop the points even on an impromptu basis. It also takes away the fear of your mind going blank at any point during the presentation. Create bullet points of the key takeaways and speak naturally about them.

Use lists of three wherever you can in your presentation. Lists of three have been used from early times up to the present day – Aristotle wrote about it in his book Rhetoric. They are particularly used by politicians and advertisers who know the value of using the rule of three to sell their ideas.

Before any speaking opportunity find out information about the audience. This will help you to tailor your speech to their needs and level of knowledge.

2. Language

Use common language whenever you can unless you are presenting a scientific or technical topic to an expert audience. When you use language that is familiar to your audience you will achieve a higher level of audience engagement. Keep acronyms to an absolute minimum. They're like speedbumps to listeners unfamiliar with them. Use short sentences. Short and concise sentences are easily heard and understood by your audience. Sub-clauses and dependent clauses require concentration. Solid and uncluttered language helps the audience with active listening, comprehension and memory of your speech.

3. Tone of Voice

Your voice can be used to highlight and underline key points, it can be used to shock, persuade or entertain. Above all, you can use your voice to maintain your audience's attention. This can be achieved by using appropriate use of ice breakers including anecdotes, shocking or controversial statistics and adept use of quotes.

An evaluation of the most popular TED talks concluded that the most successful speakers have 30.5% higher vocal variety. Before you can refine your voice for your presentations, you must first know how you sound to others. Recording yourself speaking is the best way to get an accurate assessment of your current vocal strengths and weaknesses.

Speak slowly and take your vocal tone down a notch or two. According to a recent study, men and women prefer female leaders with masculine voices. In addition, men also prefer male leaders with masculine voices. However, women do not discriminate between male voices. Most of us remember the change to a deeper tone in Margaret Thatcher's voice once she rose to Prime Minister, which was of course very deliberate and the result of professional coaching.

4. Audience

Unless you know you're facing a hostile group of people, human nature is such that your audience wants you to succeed. They're on your side! They aren't an anonymous sea of faces, but real people. Think of ways to engage your audience, such as:

- Ask rhetorical questions
- Maintain eye contact for a second or two with as many people as possible
- Be provocative
- Be challenging
- Change the pace of your delivery

- Change the volume of your voice

People want to listen to someone who is interesting, relaxed, and comfortable. In the routine conversations we have every day, we have no problem being ourselves. Yet too often, when we stand up to give a speech, something changes. We focus on the “public” at the expense of the “speaking.” To become an effective public speaker, you must do just the opposite: focus on the speaking and let go of the “public.” Think of it as a conversation between you and the audience. If you can carry on a relaxed conversation with one or two people, you can give a great speech.

5. Mistakes Happen

Even the most accomplished public speaker will make a mistake at some point. Just keep in mind that you will notice more than anyone in your audience. The most important thing a speaker can do after making a mistake is to keep going. Don’t stop and—unless the mistake was truly earth shattering—never apologise to the audience for a minor slip. A mistake can actually work for you, because it allows you to connect with your audience. They will relate much more easily to someone who is real.

6. Storytelling

Storytelling is a powerful tool used by the best speakers. By employing context into your speech for your audience to connect with, you’re creating an easy to listen to atmosphere. Whatever the topic, audiences respond best when speakers personalise their communication. Take every opportunity to put a face on the facts of your presentation. People like to hear about other people’s experiences—the triumphs, tragedies, and everyday humorous anecdotes that make up their lives. Whenever possible, insert a personal-interest element in your public speaking. Not only will it make your listeners warm up to you, but it will also do wonders at putting you at ease.

Most conference and network presentations are a short 10-15 minutes. For a 10-minute presentation take the first 2 minutes and use it to tell your audience something about yourself. Keep it light and interesting. Telling them a little bit about yourself helps build rapport. It will also help you to feel more comfortable standing up there. After that take the focus off yourself and shift it to your audience. After all, the objective is not to benefit the speaker but to benefit the audience through teaching, motivation, or entertainment.

7. Leave Them Wanting More

When it comes to public speaking, less is usually more. Always make your presentation just a bit shorter than anticipated. Give your audience just enough information to leave them wanting to learn more. Leave them energised, not overwhelmed and you will leave them with impact. Say what you need to say and use any remaining time for questions & answers.

Good speeches on any subject are made up of three parts:

- Beginning —the first words out of a speaker’s mouth need to get the audience’s attention and make them eager to hear what the speaker has to say.
- Middle — where a speaker expounds on his subject. The middle is where information is imparted from the speaker to the audience. Information needs to be given in a clear and orderly way without repetition.
- End that is as close to The Beginning as possible and leaves the audience with a “sound byte” and powerful message.

Really great public speakers always end on a high. The more you practice, the more successful you will be. Start by speaking at small events and then build up to bigger ones. Say yes as much as possible to every speaking opportunity.

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